

SYSTEMATIC-ACTIVE APPROACH METHOD IN CHEMISTRY LESSONS

Nigora Jumaniyozova Khudayberdiyevna

Khorezm Region Urganch Sahar General Secondary School No. 1

Chemistry teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7529115>

Annotation: In this article, the integration of school-institute-school is discussed and explained based on the system-active approach to training students.

Key words: systematic-active approach, school, student, chemistry, formation.

The method of teaching, in which the student does not receive knowledge in a finished form, but in the process of his educational and cognitive activity, is called the method of activity. According to A. Disterweg, the method of teaching is universal. Accordingly, it should work not only in primary classes, but also in all schools, even universities. This method is suitable for every student, where knowledge has not yet been acquired. In this context, today's pedagogy is very interested in activity-based learning technologies. The use of such technologies allows not only to arm the student with knowledge, but also to form his ability to act competently. Accordingly, learning should be a means of teaching action. Acquisition of knowledge does not occur before the beginning of the activity, but directly in its process, in the process of applying this knowledge in practice and because of such application. It is known that a person best acquires the knowledge that he uses in his practical actions, that he uses in solving some real problems.

A distinctive feature of the new standard is its activity, which makes the development of the student's personality the main goal. The main task of the teacher is to organize and create conditions that shape the actions of students. The uniqueness of the science of "chemistry" allows us to identify many ways to achieve this goal, of which we can give only some examples:

- ❖ *use of various forms of chemical experiments (illustrative, research, problem) to understand and implement educational situations;*
- ❖ *effective combination of classroom and extracurricular forms of educational process organization, organization of intellectual and creative contests, educational and research activities.*

I will tell you in more detail about the use of chemical experiments in the implementation of a systematic-active approach to the study of the topic "Metals" in the 9th grade. The experiment allows not only to discover new facts, but also to correct mistakes in students' knowledge, to clarify and correct

their understanding of some issues of the chemistry course, as well as to draw conclusions. A generalizing character. The topic "Metals" is one of the topics that experience is present in almost every lesson. The practical content of the content includes experiments on the interaction of metals with water, solutions of non-metals, salts and alkalis, experiments on corrosion and protection of metals from corrosion, qualitative reactions to metal ions, physical properties can be demonstrated. Laboratory experiments are widely used in the formation of experimental skills and acquisition of new knowledge, which students perform independently in class or according to the attached instructions, because they are easy to do, but at the same time they have a strong impact on the students' emotions. makes a secret. These include, first of all, the recognition of metal salts, determination of the ability of metals to react when interacting with solutions of diluted acids, salts and alkalis, and other experimental tasks. Students observe, analyze the obtained data, explain them theoretically and draw conclusions during the experiment conducted based on a certain plan.

Experimental tasks are a continuation of laboratory experiments performed in the classroom. Pupils are invited to expand the range of studied phenomena or demonstrate their own small inventions (find out the composition of drugs in a home first aid kit, the composition of various metal ions in them, determine the presence of water in gasoline or oil) and participate in project activities directs to do. Practical work is a combination of elements of generalization and control of knowledge at the same time. During such activities, students deeply study the essence of experiments, think about their results and try to answer the questions that inevitably arise in the process of their formation. It is important that the experiment does not acquire an interesting character, the purpose of the experiments should be clear to the students from the beginning: to prove the truth of the theoretical position, to confirm or reject the working hypothesis. In order to expand the volume of experimental information, qualitatively and completely generalize the material, the content of the experiment in practical work is slightly different from the visual experiment used in the study of new material. In my opinion, this additionally allows for a higher level of knowledge acquisition: students can apply their knowledge not only in a standard situation, but also in a similar, familiar situation, and some students are more advanced can reach the level - creative application of knowledge to solve problems. only learning situations.

The main part of the problem-solving and research experiment is the optional activities for extracurricular activities. . A problematic experience can be both collective and individual. But in both cases, students acquire research skills: independently put forward hypotheses, draw up a research plan, process the obtained results and draw conclusions. These skills allow students to participate in project activities within the school's scientific community. With the concentric structure of the studied material, students first get a simplified idea of some chemical phenomena. Transferring these simplified images to more complex objects leads to errors (the interaction of metals with nitric acid and concentrated sulfuric acid, the interaction of active metals with salt solutions, etc.).

Misunderstandings in the selection can be eliminated. Educational activities and elective topics are interrelated, they are distinguished only by the level of complexity of the material, which allows the use of problematic experiments (first of all, the content of experiments is related to phenomena and laws known to students should be based on a possible problematic situation, that is, the student should be in the zone of immediate development, secondly, other experiences that lead to an understanding of the problem based on the existing knowledge before these experiences should be shown; thirdly, experiences in which the problem is posed. interest awakening, arousing interest.) will be continued in the students' design work.

Through the science of "Chemistry", it is possible to create conditions for students to start their actions, significantly increase their knowledge, concretize it, clarify it, and systematize it. This is confirmed by the achievements of students in examinations, intellectual and creative competitions, and the results of educational activities. Thus, it is possible to satisfy their cognitive needs and develop individual interests, which helps to increase professional competence in general [9. As an example, let's evaluate the skills diagnosed when performing a contextual task on the topic "Nitrogen". Nitrogen. One of the most common elements on Earth. The main component of air (78.09% of the volume), its separation produces industrial nitrogen (more than $\frac{3}{4}$ goes to ammonia synthesis). Nitrogen is one of the main biogenic elements that make up proteins and nucleic acids. Nitrogen is produced industrially by fractional distillation of liquid air.

Thus, contextual tasks help the formation of the ability to solve real practical problems and functional skills, open wide opportunities for evaluating the level of creative development, the potential of a person.

References:

1. Stupnitskaya M.A. What is a study project? / M.: First September, 20.
2. The concept of federal state educational standards general education: project / RAO; ed. A. M. Kondakova, A. A.
3. Kuznetsova. - M.: Marifat, 2008. - (Second generation standards). Z. Surin Yu.V. Problematic experience as one of the chemical forms of experience // Chemistry at school. No. 9, 2007.
4. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.
5. Verbitsky A.A. Active learning in higher education: a contextual approach: 1 - Method. allowance.- M.: Higher School, 1991.- 207 p.

